

THE COST OF ADVERTISING IN TODAY'S GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract: It is known that development in our country and in the world is taking place very quickly, but as a result of this, negative aspects are also developing, which we can say about several aspects that are encountered in the education of young people. This article discusses the scientific and practical importance of propaganda and campaigning to overcome the above issues in the current era of globalization.

Key words: Education and training, spirituality, globalization, ideological thought, promotion and agitation activities, educational system, reform.

It is known from the world experience that every country has implemented human capital, in particular, by improving the scientific, creative and spiritual potential of the young generation, in order to increase its development and expand the development factors. Today, at the initiative of the head of our state, reforms in the field of education of young people and raising their spirituality are closely connected with other areas of our life and are being systematically implemented.

On January 28, 2022, our President announced "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" signed the decree. Also, on this very day, January 28, 2022, a video selector meeting was held under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev on issues of school education development. As the head of our state emphasizes that school education and youth education is a matter of life and death, such an approach to youth education in the current globalization environment will undoubtedly bring its positive results. Because the family, school, and neighborhood create favorable conditions for young people to get closer and bond with each other. It is known that raising a child is the main task of the family, and this task has been and continues to be actively performed by the state and society due to its importance not only in the family, but also socially.

In order to continue these values and traditions, the time itself requires us to further improve propaganda work with live examples that reveal the foundations of spirituality, enlightenment and national ideology.

In this sense, instilling the heritage, national traditions, customs and values left by our great ancestors into the minds of our youth in more effective ways is of great importance in raising them to be intellectually complete and mature, in the formation of the sense of identity, patriotism, and involvement in reforms in young people.

In order to implement these tasks, the Ministry of Public Education, the Republican Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment, the Union of Writers and the Creative Union of Journalists have adopted a joint decision "On the introduction of the position of propagandist on creative and cultural issues in general secondary educational institutions" in our republic. according to the conclusion, a propagandist on creative and cultural issues was appointed to 10,008 secondary schools. This position of "Propagist on creative and cultural issues" is reserved for

each general education institution, and writers, poets, journalists, and creative teachers are appointed to this position.

Perfect morals and good character are formed gradually. People's moral criteria, values, spiritual heritage of the past are connected with the old motherland. That is why our moral ideas, our school of manners, our national values and traditions, and our cultural heritage will arouse respect and admiration in others only if they ultimately serve the nation, its reputation and prospects, and only then will our young people learn about their past, identity, values, and traditions. does not forget Good qualities, customs, traditions, national values and the figure of our great grandfathers, their historical heritage will illuminate the path of generations with a brighter light.

Alisher Navoi, Sa'di, Jami, Beruni, Farobi, Fuzuli, who glorified the ideas of humanity, love and compassion, decency, and friendship of peoples in order to raise our national consciousness and spirit, get to know our ancestors, our identity, and properly educate the future and current generations. The works of great thinkers such as Omar Khayyam and Bedil are widely used. In our work in this field, we study the works of religious figures who promoted universal values, including muhaddiths like Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Imam Moturudi, Burkhaniddin Marginani, Ahmad Yassavi, Sufi Ollayor, Rabguzi, Ghazali, Bahauddin Naqshband, Khoja Ahror, and Islamic theologians. , new analysis-interpretations of their works arouse great interest in people.

Today, in all corners of the new Uzbekistan, our great historical monuments are being restored and turned into landmarks, and the preservation of our immortal national values leads to a deeper understanding of our identity.

It is known that the current era is a time when the world's ideological contradictions have become complex, and ideological landfills are becoming stronger than nuclear landfills. The whole earth is the only space for mankind. But in history, there have been countless wars to change existing borders and conquer certain territories. In this process, the weapons of war were constantly improved. Until the 20th century, these wars were mostly between one or two countries or regions. Dozens of countries and countries of several continents participated in the two world wars that took place in the 20th century.

So, the weapons of war continued to improve. Today, they are enough to destroy life on the entire planet several times, let alone conquer another territory. By the end of the 20th century, humanity faced a number of problems that knew no bounds. War and peace, environmental disasters, spiritual poverty, drug business, terrorism are among these problems.

By the beginning of the 21st century, the interaction between the countries of the world has become so strong that there is not a single country that is completely surrounded by this process. The impact of globalization on different countries is also different. This situation is related to the economic, informational, spiritual potential and politics of the countries of the world.

Globalization (globalization) is derived from the Latin word "glob", which can be translated as "rounding", "organization". It is used to explain the transformation of the globe, the globe, into a whole globe, a sphere, due to the scientific and technical achievements of mankind. Human development is the process of development of production forces. This process took thousands of years, piece by piece...

Globalization is an increase in interaction and connection between the economy, culture, spirituality, and people of different countries. There are many definitions of globalization. In the definition of the French researcher B. Bundy, it is emphasized that the process of globalization is 3-dimensional:

- ② Globalization is a continuous historical process.
- ② Globalization is the process of homogenization (homogeneous) and universalization of the world.
- ② Globalization is the process of "washing away" of national borders.

Russian A.Parshev defines globalization as follows: "In fact, the main content of globalization is to absorb the added value of products produced in other countries, the main resources of the world."

A famous Indian statesman on the positive and negative effects of globalization on the economic policies and morals of countries of Mahatma Gandhi well expressed in the following words: "I cannot keep the gates and doors of my house closed all the time, because fresh air must enter my house. At the same time, I don't want the air coming in through my open doors and windows to turn my house upside down and knock me down."

Therefore, it can be understood that the idea of national independence is a factor of protecting our homes and lives from "hurricanes" by providing us with fresh air in the process of globalization today.

The positive aspect of globalization is that it accelerates the convergence of nations, states, national cultures and economies, and opens new opportunities for their development.

The great socio-political changes that took place at the end of the 20th century, the breakdown of the relative balance as a result of the end of the bipolar world, fundamentally changed the world's ideological landscape.

The 20th century was a period of sharp and complex ideological confrontations in the world. At the end of the 20th century, as a result of the end of the bipolar world and the disruption of the relative balance, the world's ideological landscape changed radically. As our first president Islam Karimov noted, "at the end of the 20th century, unique changes are taking place in the world in terms of geographical and political importance and scale. These changes are unique. They require not only to think deeply about the views and their mechanisms, but also to re-evaluate them in many ways. Many rules, principles and ideas that are the basis of international relations during the "Cold War" are required to be fundamentally revised. The whole world is becoming an integrated and interdependent system, in which there is no room for self-satisfaction and limitation. This situation makes it necessary to develop completely new approaches when forming current international relations, interacting with international structures and participating in their activities».

Today, humanity has made great progress. His thinking is reaching towards infinity. The distant universe searches for news from the depths of the bottomless earth. At the beginning of our topic, we emphasized the idea that as consciousness and thinking grows, various vices and corruptions aimed at derailing the lives of others continue in the spirituality of people. Continuing our thoughts on this, we can say that in fact this is an eternal struggle between opposition, good and evil. Man is a victim of the eternal struggle between these two poles. He has already realized this struggle between the goodness and corruption of the world, but realizing it, unfortunately, he himself has become an active participant in this struggle, ready

to destroy one and the other and lead the other to decline. The destructive forces created by man are capable of destroying the earth not once, but several times.

Today we must step very carefully. Especially, we need to protect our children who have not yet hardened their bones from the attack of evil forces and educate them carefully. So that various mischiefs don't take root in their pure and tender hearts. After all, they are our future, tomorrow's owners of today's development. Cultivating goodness in the hearts of young people is a guarantee of preserving the purity of their spirituality and national spirituality. Only a nation with its own national spirituality and culture can preserve itself as a people and a nation. In order to preserve such precious values, it is the need of the time to carry out propaganda and propaganda work.

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